

Marginality in Mahesh Dattani's *on a Muggy Night in Mumbai*

Dr, Rajendra Raghunath Rajput

Associate Professor of English

Dhanaji Nana Mahavidyalaya,

Faizpur, Maharashtra

<https://orcid.org/0009-0004-8384-9540>

Abstract

Mahesh Dattani, the most influential Indian dramatist reveals his genius through the representation of the suppressed invisible issues. He has extended horizon of Indian drama in English by voicing the issues of eunuchs, homosexuals and suppressed human beings. The man-woman, man-man, women-women relationships grow frustration and nothingness in the middle-class society. The present paper aims at exploring the world of the lesbians and gays as they have denied equal rights to live with in the society. It is revealed in his play, *On a Muggy Night in Mumbai* very poignantly. The playwright explores the love-hate relationship among gays and lesbians both at psychological and physical level. The play soothes the attitude of the society.

Keywords: Homosexuals, gays, lesbians, eunuchs, love-hate relationship.

Recently, Supreme Court has passed the judgment that article 377 is not suitable and applicable to homosexuals. This stirs the world and forced to rethink about the stigma attached to homosexuals in the so-called sophisticated society. The term ‘homosexuality’ is used for a homosexual who is sexually attracted to others of the same sex.” (Oxford 747) The term, ‘homosexual’ implies sexual relationship between the same genders. Homosexuals are gay and lesbians. The common terms used for homosexuals are *lesbian* for females and *gay* for males. It is difficult to estimate gay or lesbian orientation for many reasons as many gay or lesbian people cannot be identified openly.

On a Muggy Night in Mumbai (1998) is a play that deals with homosexual relations in the urban society. It is adapted to a film, *Mango Soufflé* (2002). The play debates the socio-psychological identity crisis of the gays. They are shattered between social taboos, subjective whims and inner conscience. It sensationalizes the torments, predicaments, insecurities, dilemma and frustrations of the gays in the materialistic society. It scrutinizes the identity crisis of the gays who inhabit non-praiseworthy space in cosmic social order. The others feel shame of gay and marginalize them.

In the play, Kamlesh and Prakash are lovers. But in due course of time Prakash transforms as Ed by feeling ashamed of being homosexual. He meets Kiran, who is Kamlesh's sister. Meanwhile, Sharad, who is still passionately in adoration with Prakash, is fulfilling Kamlesh's sexual needs. Incidentally, Prakash bumps into the life of Kamlesh as a lover of his sister, Kiran. Ed wants to hide his gay identity and to marry Kiran. He longs to remain in touch with Kamlesh through Kiran so that nobody will suspect his identity. When Kiran knows the relationship, she displays all her compassion for the gay community and homosexual associations. On the other hand, Deepali is a ‘sensible’ lesbian in the group. She feels compassionate for Kamlesh and has an affinity towards him. She is vocal of her sexual inclinations in her arguments at the party. The guard is a homosexual who is seen putting up his attires in front of Kamlesh just at the commencement of the play. Ranjit who desires to obscure his gay identity in India has his gay partner residing in England. These characters show the invisible world of gays and lesbians in the society.

The play compacts with unisexual and bisexual love relationships. None takes bold initiative of declaring in the open about their sexual orientation. The playwright highlights the burning issue of gays in the society. Every person next door may be a homosexual but restrains him from exposing his real self and thus endures with the pretence of heterosexual. The play dares to revitalize the facade of sexlessness from male-male intimacy, dealing with homosexuality. It dispenses with conventional and so-called orthodox, man/woman role-playing. The play is a treasure house of all the homosexual characters Kamlesh, Sharad, Ed, Ranjit, Bunny and Deepali simultaneously breathing in two different worlds. Sharad as the gay man speaks to the lesbian and both are intelligent. Homosexuality is not a fatal disease or mental illness that requires to be, cured. Homosexuals are as a common man. They are excluded just because they love 'their own kind'. They get cruel treatment from the society. They are regarded as 'queers' Homosexuals are typical humans attracted to their own gender. They sustain in their own make-over world temporarily liberal from any restrains and societal regulations.

The action takes place in the living room of Kamlesh, a fashion designer living in Mumbai. It is divided into three acts. In Act I, the stage is divided into three action areas. The first is a small flat, beautifully done up in 'ethnic chic' fashion. The windows overlook the Mumbai skyline and act literally as a window to the city with its glittering lights. The flat is located in the up-market area of Marine Drive. It speaks a lot of its occupant, Kamlesh and his attempt at creating a world where he can belong. The second area, a completely non – realistic set comprising three levels, is black and expansive. Characters in this area are immediately suspended in a 'shoonya' where they are forced to confront their inner thoughts. Below this is Kamlesh's bedroom. The bedroom is realistic, but hidden behind a gauze wall, giving it mystery and secrecy. The backdrop of these three acting areas is the Mumbai skyline; engulfing the created world of Kamlesh, the secret private space of the bedroom and the deeper space that belongs to the inner thoughts of the characters.

The scene shifts to airport lounge. Kiran, Kamlesh's sister arrives. She is in late thirties. She is engaged to Ed. Ed's former name is Prakash. Prakash had been the sex partner of Kamlesh earlier. Now he wants to come out of it. He appears on the

scene. Kiran is totally unaware about relationship between Kamlesh and Prakash. Kamlesh to forget Prakash but still he finds it difficult to come out of it. The scene shifts to the flat of Kamlesh. Kamlesh, Kiran, Sharad gather together. Sharad is also in love with Kamlesh. But Kamlesh is still interested in Prakash. In absence of Prakash, Kamlesh uses Sharad just to fill in the vacuum. Unfortunately, Sharad is not able to fulfil Kamlesh's emotional craving for Prakash. He feels sorry for involving with Kamlesh. He blames Kamlesh:

(Over Kamlesh) And I am not being a drama queen. Now this is being a drama queen ... (shrieks with arms akimbo.) I wasted a year of my life being a house wife for you and all I get is a kick in the ass! you beast! (pause lights a cigarette) Sorry. That wasn't really funny. Although some people might think it is. Things could be worse like (points to the window) that woman I couldn't take it for a minute when you said you didn't love me, but she... She can't throw him out. (CP 56)

Sharad knows Kamlesh's attempt to forget Prakash is not genuine. It is because Kamlesh has carefully treasured his photograph with Prakash. It is clear that Kamlesh is still obsessed by the thoughts of Prakash. Deepali is one more visitor invited by Kamlesh for the party. She is friendly with everyone. She is aware of the love relationship between Kamlesh-Prakash and Sharad. She is lesbian. She is in love with Tina, one who never appears on the stage. Deepali comes in. She comes to know that Kamlesh has used the Guard to gratify his sex hunger. She doesn't like it. There enter Ranjit and Bunny Singh. Ranjit works with HIV counselors in England. It is his opinion that the condition of homosexuals in England is better than India. Bunny Singh, a famous T.V actor plays the role in serials. He is projected as a social reformer. He too is a gay. For public he is a social reformer but in reality he hides the truth that he is gay. He is afraid that public will not accept him if he disclose the truth about him.

Kamlesh feels lonely in Bombay. Memories of Prakash haunt him. He decides to consult a psychiatrist. The psychiatrist advises him to reorient himself. But he finds it impossible for himself. Bunny Singh asks him to adjust with surrounding, reorient himself and hide the reality. But everything tried is of no use for Kamlesh because his

love for same sex is inborn and incurable. Hence, he cannot come out of his love for Prakash. He opens his wound to Ranjit:

I tried explaining to him (psychiatrist) that I needed his help to overcome my anxiety and fears, not to be something I am not. Could he help me cope with his? (pause). I don't go to him anymore. I stopped taking his pills. The fear has come back. I am obsessed even more by the memory of Prakash. I—I feel I cannot live without him. I am capable of doing anything. (pause) Please help me! Who do we turn to except one another? (CP 69-70)

Bunny Sing asks Kamlesh to get marry with a woman and continue his homosexuality. But Kamlesh is honest with himself and doesn't want to live with mask. Sharad asks him to exercise his will power to forget Prakash. He wants Kamlesh to tear up his photograph with Prakash in the presence of all party members. He says: "Now take a look at the picture. And say it out loud –'As my friends, this city and God are witness to my vow, I break all ties with Prakash.' Then you will tear up that picture and throw it out of the window. Is that clear?" (CP 73)

Kamlesh tries to tear the picture but he can't do that. Kiran enters. Kamlesh introduces Kiran to everyone. She is surprised to see Bunny Sing among all homosexuals. She thinks Bunny as an ideal husband and father. On being asked, Bunny doesn't clear himself whether he is a gay or not. But one thing is sure that he tolerates gay. Kiran is engaged now with Ed (Prakash). Her first marriage was failure. She announces her marriage schedule: "We are having a Hindu wedding in Bangalore for my parents next month on the 7th. And a Tamil Christian wedding on the 12th for Ed and his family here in Juhu Church. I hope you will be free to attend." (CP 77)

Kiran suspects that something is wrong with her brother, Kamlesh. Nobody present disclose the reality to her. Deepali just tells her that Kamlesh is under depression. Kamlesh re-enters. He doesn't want his sister to know about his homosexual relationship with Prakash/ Ed. Somehow, he manages to send Kiran into another room. Act II opens with a story of the first meeting between Prakash and Kamlesh. Prakash had been in the park where gays wonder in search of partners. Prakash, the closet homosexual had met Kamlesh in the park on one of the evening. Since then they were in love with each other. The scene again shifts to Kamlesh's

flat. Deepali wants that Kamlesh should tell Kiran everything about his relationship with Prakash. She wants Kamlesh and Kiran to be happy in future and should not live under the constant fear of being exposed. Sharad also blames Kamlesh for ruining Kiran's life in such a way. Bunny Singh is of the opinion that Deepali and Sharad are unnecessarily making the thing worse. Deepali corrects Bunny Singh by saying that it is impossible to love man and woman at a time with the same intensity. Pretension of any relationship does not last long. Bunny Singh admits the truth. Kamlesh believes that Prakash is 'straight' now and hence heterosexual. He adds: "He (Prakash) goes to church every week now. They put him on to a psychiatrist. He believes his love for me was the work of the devil. Now the devil has left him." (CP 85)

Kamlesh also is of the opinion that Kiran has found a good husband in Prakash and they would be happy as husband and wife. He loves his sister. He expresses his concern as Kiran comes out of the bathroom.

Very slowly she began to find herself again. And I would pray that she would not fall apart again. I was thankful also for Prakash for making her happy again. I don't think it ever occurred to her in her wildest dreams that we were lovers. She never even asked me whether Prakash was gay. She just assumed he wasn't. (CP 86)

Sharad is about to tell something to Kiran. Kamlesh loses his temper and asks him to get out of his house. As Sharad goes out, Kiran goes after him to bring him back. The scene again shifts back into the past. Ed and Kiran talk to one another about their plan of marriage. At the end of this scene, it is revealed that both Kamlesh and Kiran love Prakash. Meanwhile Ed also enters in Kamlesh's flat.

Act III opens in the living room of Kamlesh. The *baraat* is passing from below the window. Everyone gathered in Kamlesh's flat is disturbed by noting freedom to the marriage between man and woman. They feel suffocated. Kamlesh and Ed try to avoid each other. Kiran doesn't understand the reason. She even doesn't understand why for Kamlesh and Sharad are separated. She requests Kamlesh and Sharad to start living together. Sharad and Deepali try to tell truth about Prakash to Kiran. Deepali asks Sharad whether he wants to be 'straight'. Ed and Bunny Singh think it possible. It is clear that these want Sharad to live double life that of hetero

and homosexual. Bunny Singh gives way to his inner feelings. He feels really sorry for living double life. He admits that he is a gay and cheating public by playing the role of an ideal husband and father as well. Thus he comes out as a real hero. The action then takes place in the drawing room as well as in the bedroom at the same time. Ed has decided to cheat the world. He has planned to get marry with Kiran and continue his relationship with Kamlesh. Kiran calls herself as a complete woman. Sharad and Deepali decide to tell the truth to Kiran. The Guard comes in and gives the photograph to Sharad which Sharad transfers it to Kiran. Kiran blames Kamlesh for hiding the truth. She asks the Ed to get out of the flat. Ed gets overwhelmed. He goes crazy and runs to climb the window. He tries to commit suicide but has no courage to jump down. Kamlesh, Bunny, Sharad and Ranjit rush to save him. The Guard helps him to walk out. He cries:

ED: (to Kamlesh). Where do I begin? How do I begin to live?

KAMLESH: I don't know. (CP 111)

The play ends without solution. It goes on moving from present to the past and from past to the present. The place of action is confined to Kamlesh's flat only. At a time two actions take place in two different parts of the flat. The time of action is evening. Most of the dialogues spoken by characters, deal with the problems of homosexuality. In short, it is unique work of art by Dattani.

On a Muggy Night in Mumbai is Dattani's path breaking play because it deals with the live issue of LGBT people. Kiran being homo's sister was ill treated by the former husband and plans to seek comfort in the company of Prakash. But finally she comes to know about homosexual relation between her brother, Kamlesh and her would be husband, Prakash. Thus, her dream of happy marriage gets shattered and she is left to repent for the rest of her life. Bunny Sing is antithesis of Kamlesh. He is secret homosexual. As Smita Lakhotiya states:

Bunny, his [Kamlesh's] antithesis, the clandestine homosexual, plays a role of a happily married father on a television sitcom as well as in the real life. But he is deceiving himself at two levels. Bunny deals with two kinds of deception: the life of social lying, of public deceit, of those who play the game of duplicity that is bound to end in scandal ruin: and the other more private

deception, the cultivation of illusion that is necessary to achieve sexual satisfaction. Bunny is rather more traditional gay man (he would say happily) while publicly denying his own nature. (61)

Ranjit is another character of gay type. He left India because India, according to him is not a country for persons like him. Now he finds himself in a safe position as he has taken an easy way out moving to Europe for the last twelve years where he is able to open himself. Thus by taking a group of homosexuals in the cosmopolitan city like Bombay, Dattani reveals their interpersonal relationships, their experiences, their self – delusions and their realizations. All of them sail in the same boat, but each has his own way of thinking. Sunanda Shelake remarks:

He [Dattani] is the first playwright who has used all the gay characters in his play *On A Muggy Night in Mumbai* to handle openly gay themes of love, affiliation, trust and betrayal, raising serious ‘closet’ issues that remain generally invisible. This is the first play in Indian theatre where the playwright points out at the male – male and female – female dealing openly with homosexuality where a gay prefers to be called ‘brown’ in West than to be called ‘homosexual’ in India. (215)

Dattani intends to establish that the subjects like homosexuality are rooted in human psyche. It is drastic on the part of playwrights to introduce an issue in theatre that is usually treated as taboo in Indian theatre. The whole presentation is arranged in such a manner that homosexuality instead of being recognized as taboo has become a natural human experience.

Works Cited

- Dattani, Mahesh. *Collected Plays*. New Delhi: Penguin Books, 2000
- Lakhotiya, Smita R. *Care and Cure, Relationship in Dattani's Plays*, Kanpur: Shubhan Publication, 2011.
- Shelake, Sunanda. *Mahesh Dattani: New voices of the Theatre*, Kanpur: Shubhan Publication, 2015.
- Wehmeier, Sally. *Oxford Advanced Learner's Dictionary*, New York: Oxford University Press, 2005.